

Earth as a Library

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The Earth has often been viewed in many ways, as a lifeboat we are all in, a garden of Eden or as a blue marble on a black field of space. What has been overlooked is that Earth is also an immense set of libraries housed in all its different forms in habitats and environments containing the blueprints for life and designs for the future. Not just the blueprints for life of organisms, plants, animals and whole ecosystems but the blueprints for undiscovered chemical formulas and reactions, designs, patterns, concepts and ideas not yet realized by us.

Our species has depended since time began on learning from these blueprints in every culture, be it from forests, lagoons, river systems, coral-reefs, grasslands or the arctic to the deep ocean bottoms. Each of these systems and organisms contain untold volumes of information. Information that researchers and scientists draw from to find out about basic natural designs, systems and patterns present in nature that can be further developed into new technologies and products.

The sum total of all wealth realized by this process in human history uses less than 3 to 5% of the information contained in the Earth libraries. We are preparing to risk 97 to 95% of all the information housed in all the different organisms, plants, animals and habitats to climate change. This would dramatically change the Earth libraries system losing some future discoveries forever. Limiting the growth of our science, technologies, arts and cultures. The different discoveries that would have been gained in all our fields of endeavors will be lost forever. This economic loss would far out shadow all economic gains made to date that have brought about climate change in the first place. We will by not doing anything, lose both our inheritance and legacy to other future generations not yet born. If we wait for others to act first, we will be waiting for a long time. It is not that politicians and business leaders will act first, for fifty to forty-five years they have talked, wrote papers, held conferences and found other ways to keep from facing up to the real issue.

How do we keep from losing our inheritance of these libraries of Earth do to climate change? The last time there was a need this great for people to join forces and act together was in World War II. This time it's climate change and the slowness of others in power.

Our mission should be, to save as much as we can.

Our objective is to learn what needs to be done, plan and do it.

Examples can be: What plants and animals can stay in place with or without help; What plants and animals need to move with the new climate range changes, with or without help. How to set up forest micro climates; How to develop and keep open migration corridors. There are excellent examples of local management by communities in the Philippines that have had great success developing and running marine protected areas (MPAs). These MPAs are managed on a local rather than a national level. As a result, these communities receive great economic benefits for protecting these areas, including the collection of use permit fees and increased employment opportunities.

Our resources are basic tools at hand:

That of human capital; along with the political system of democracy for inclusion and diversity (very important); open source technologies that are free of costly copyright and patents; education and literacy for learning and information sharing. Add to this using lessons from the past of: 'teach-ins' (informal lecture and discussion or series of lectures on a subject of public interest like climate change and what one person or small groups can do) and informational campaigns in the press, news and social media; forming alliances with other groups for growing general support; helping reform some environmental organizations that have lost their way; using the power of the vote to recall politicians who have clearly lost their way. Holding marches, rallies and using non-violence protests to stop destructive processes.

There is over 101 things to do that are not on this short list. What is the point of this all? To be effective we need to organize, network, plan and draw on the best knowledge possible in all fields. But most of all we need to take back the phrase 'sustainable development' from the political / public relations machine that took it over, and change it back to its true meaning, 'a fight for survival'. Saving ever thing we can of the Libraries of Earth is not only a good idea but it makes good economic, business, political and military sense as well. Side issues of refugees, limited strategic natural resources, falling food supplies are all symptoms of the root cause not the only issues of the day.

Those that stand in the way of dealing effectively with climate change are willing to make money from genocide and crimes against humanity. There has never been a shortage of them in our collective history. Each basic blueprint / design library (habitat and ecosystem) of Earth we lose to climate change and intransigence of others will diminish our creativeness as a species and future for all time.